

Field Course in Sequence Stratigraphy (Chapada Diamantina, Bahia)

from basin fill to reservoir zonation

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Support

Field Course Sequence Stratigraphy (Chapada Diamantina - Ba): from basin fill to reservoir zonation

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1. Introduction and Objectives

Petrobras elaborated and conducted the first field course on sequence stratigraphy in Brazil in 1997 (Savini and Raja Gabaglia, 1977; Magalhães et al., 2014a). Since then, Petrobras has been delivering it to several groups. Except for Petrobras, Magalgeoconsulting is the only company to deliver an equivalent course in the Chapada Diamantina area for the geoscientist community.

Sequence stratigraphy is a method based on the identification and correlation of stratal stacking patterns in the sedimentary record (Catuneanu, 2022). Such an approach helps understand sedimentation evolution through time and space in sedimentary basins. Currently, the stratigraphic analysis that supports the exploration and production of natural resources are founded on comprehending the sedimentary processes that generated the deposits and their bounding surfaces (Magalhães et al., 2021). The exploration and production of natural resources generated by or related to sedimentary processes depend upon building chronostratigraphic frameworks that allow palaeogeographic reconstructions, which in turn improve our knowledge about the temporal and spatial distribution of source rocks, seals and petroleum reservoirs, and other natural resources deposits.

The field course has a methodological and practical objective aimed at recognising stacking patterns, identifying surfaces and stratigraphic sequences and their rank based on observations on outcrops. Participants use Virtual Outcrop Models (VOMs) to integrate all data they gather with Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) and Gamma Ray logs from outcrops. As a result, participants build a chronostratigraphic framework from the basin-fill scale (1st order) to the reservoir scale (4th order). In vogue in the petroleum industry, this approach is also applied to other natural resources production optimisation, C and H storage and pollutants injection. The expected gain in stratigraphic analysis skills will help the participants deal with other outcrops, well logs, cores and seismic data.

At the end of the course, participants are expected to:

- Grasp the sequence stratigraphy principles and methodology;
- Build chronostratigraphic frameworks suitable to the production and exploration of petroleum and other natural resources, storage of C and H, and pollutants injection;
- Comprehend the impact this approach has on fluid injection and production performance of hydrocarbons and other natural resources;
- Apply high-resolution sequence stratigraphy to reservoir zonation and characterisation or other natural resource deposits.

1.1. Study area

The Chapada Diamantina region is located in the central Bahia State. Meso- to Neoproterozoic metasedimentary rocks crop out in the area representing aeolian, glacial, alluvial, deltaic, tide-influenced estuarine and shallow marine depositional systems, which are analogues to those found in Phanerozoic sedimentary basins. The world-class outcrops allow detailed analysis of the stacking pattern for dozens of meters and accurate lateral correlation through dozens of kilometres. Despite the transformations triggered by diagenesis and very-low metamorphic grade during the Brazilian event, the rocks exhibit exceptionally well-preserved primary sedimentary structures. Such a combination turns Chapada Diamantina into a unique laboratory in Brazil to apply high-resolution sequence stratigraphy to reservoir zonation and characterisation. The area is, therefore, suitable to apply the principles of sequence stratigraphy at the outcrop scale, focusing on the exploration and production of hydrocarbon and other natural resources. The studied outcrops belong to Tombador Formation, in the whereabouts of Lençóis city, and Mangabeira Formation, close to Seabra city, at the shoulder of BR-242 road. The main access to Lençóis is the BR-242 road from the Chapada Diamantina airport (Figs. 1 and 2).

Fig. 1. Outcrops' location by the BR-242 road. See the outcrops' list in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Study area geological map and structural cross-section, with outcrops' list (modified from Guadagnin et al., 2015).

2. Agenda

Day 1: Arrival in Lençóis, course opening, Terrain Digital Model (MDT) and agenda.

Day 2: Lectures. Morning: Regional geology, Sequence stratigraphy. Afternoon: Visiting Pai Inácio anticline. Lectures: Aeolian depositional system and the course methodology. Photointerpretation/3D outcrop model.

Day 3: Morning, Fieldwork: aeolian outcrop 1. Afternoon, Hotel: Closing aeolian outcrop. Photointerpretation/3D outcrop model Ponte outcrop 2.

Day 4: Morning: Fieldwork Ponte outcrop. Afternoon: Groups presentation along the outcrop. Hotel: Closing Ponte, identification of 3rd order sequence stratigraphic surfaces and systems tracts.

Day 5: Photointerpretation/3D outcrop model and fieldwork Morro do Pai Inácio outcrop 3. Closing in the field.

Day 6: Lecture alluvial fan. Fieldwork: 3rd order stratigraphic correlation outcrops 5 to 13.

Day 7: Morning – High-resolution sequence stratigraphy applied to reservoir zonation and characterization. Exercises on 3rd and 4th order stratigraphic correlation. Afternoon - Unravelling an original oil-saturated zone in Fazenda Santa Luzia oilfield, onshore Brazil: field rejuvenation through increased production and oil recovery factor. Course closing and feedback from participants.

Day 8: Departure to Salvador City.

3. Course methodology

This field course presents the up-to-date high-resolution sequence stratigraphy method. The method was consolidated by Petrobras High-Resolution Sequence Stratigraphy School (e.g. Fragoso et al., 2023, 2022, 2021; Magalhães et al., 2023, 2021, 2020, 2017, 2016; Melo et al., 2021, 2020). Besides, the course uses VOMs, GPR lines, and GR logs to be integrated with data gathered by the participants (sedimentological, stratigraphic, structural) to support their interpretations.

Before the fieldwork, participants use orthophotos and MVAs to interpret architectural elements and bounding surfaces, faults and fractures and to indicate the location of sedimentological logs to be measured on the outcrops. Once the sedimentological logs are ready, participants interpret the sequence stratigraphy surfaces and update their mapping on the orthophotos. Integrating all groups' sedimentological logs lead to a discussion regarding the surface's hierarchies and the individualisation of medium- and high-frequency sequences.

The following methodological steps must be followed. Steps 1 to 3 and 8 are done at the Hotel. Steps 4 to 7 are done in the field:

Step 1: Delimiting architectural elements based on internal sedimentary structures on orthophotos, GPR lines and VOMs;

Step 2: Interpreting stratal stacking patterns and correlating high-resolution sequence stratigraphic surfaces;

Step 3: Defining the sedimentological logs' locations;

Step 4: Logging the outcrop. The sedimentological log must include depositional facies description and palaeocurrent directions;

Step 5: Detailed characterisation of architectural elements. Depositional systems' interpretation;

Step 6: Interpreting stacking patterns based on the vertical recurrence of architectural elements;

Step 7: Identifying and correlating high-resolution sequence stratigraphic surfaces. Individualising high-frequency sequences on the sedimentological log, orthophoto and VOM. Comparing with the previous interpretation (Step 2);

Step 8: Integrating the sedimentological logs. Discussion about the candidate surfaces to be ranked at the immediately higher hierarchy and identification of their systems tracts.

4. Geotectonic evolution of São Francisco craton

The studied strata belong to Espinhaço Supergroup (Proterozoic aeon). This unit crops out at the centre-north portion of the São Francisco craton in the Chapada Diamantina domain (Fig. 3).

The São Francisco and Congo cratons are Archean/Palaeoproterozoic blocks from a single continental mass that broke up in the Cretaceous during the Atlantic Ocean opening (Pedreira and De Waele, 2008). Those cratons either represent a piece from the Rodinia supercontinent, which was assembled 1.0 Ga (Brito Neves et al., 1999; Campos Neto, 2000), or an isolated continent that was not part of Rodinia (Kröner and Cordani, 2003; Pisarevsky et al., 2003). The São Francisco and other South American and African cratons are currently understood as part of interior continental plates and, therefore, relatively stable portions of tectonic plates that were consolidated in the Neoproterozoic to assemble the Western Gondwana continent (Brito Neves et al., 1999; Campos Neto, 2000; Alkmim et al., 2004).

The São Francisco craton covers a vast area of Brazil's Minas Gerais and Bahia states. It is a crustal segment consolidated in the Palaeoproterozoic and is bounded by the following Brazilian orogenic belts (Late Proterozoic): Brasília, Araçuaí, Sergipana, Rio Preto and Riacho do Pontal (Fig. 3; Almeida, 1977). The south limit was redefined by Cruz (2004), and the basement is composed of rocks older than 1.8 Ga, which consist of Archean medium- and high-grade metamorphic terrains (granites and greenstones associations from Gavião, Jequié, Serrinha and Itabuna-Salvador-Curaçá blocks). These four crustal segments were soldered during the Tramazonian orogeny (Fig. 4; Barbosa and Sabaté, 2004) and later covered by Proterozoic and Phanerozoic strata. In the central part, the Palaeo- to Mesoproterozoic Espinhaço Supergroup filled up a rift system whose bottom portion was intruded by plutonic rocks. During the Late Proterozoic, glacial and marine siliciclastic and carbonate were deposited (Pedrosa-Soares et al., 2011a).

Fig. 3. Geological map of São Francisco craton (adapted from Delgado et al., 2003 and Alkmim, 2004). Note the Chapada Diamantina Basin's location.

Diamantina, Bahia (modified from Barbosa and Sabaté, 2004). The continental collision between Gavião (in Brazil) and Gabon (in Africa) blocks is registered in folds and thrust faults with WNW vergency that are observed in the Jacobina-Contendas-Mirante (JCM) lineament, over which a transpressional sinistral regime was superimposed (Barbosa, 1997; Leite, 2002, Barbosa and Sabaté, 2004; Alkmim, 2004).

The tectonic evolution of the São Francisco craton may be summarised in the following steps (Figs. 5 and 6; Alkmim, 2004; Pedrosa-Soares and Alkmim, 2011):

Agglutination and consolidation of a huge Archean continental mass: between 2.8-2.6 Ga, which assembled older than 3.4 Ga different continental nuclei;

Individualization of the Paramirim continent: the Siderian tafrogenese, circa 2.5 Ga, broke up the continental mass that evolved to passive margins;

Transamazonian orogeny (Rhyacian/Orosirian, 2.3-2.15 Ga): The Archean Gavião, Jequié, Serrinha and Itabuna-Salvador-Curaçá blocks were assembled. This is the region's crust formation main period;

Statherian tafrogenese (1.8–1.6 Ga): The older rifting event affected the São Francisco-Conglo plate after its agglutination (Brito-Neves et al., 1995). Although well documented in São Francisco craton, this event is yet to be identified in Western Congo and Congo craton surrounding areas (Tack et al., 2001). Ensialic rifts with vulcanism were superimposed in the supercontinent formed in the previous step. Sediments from Espinhaço Supergroup were deposited in these rift-sag basins. The onset of the Espinhaço rifting was associated with:

- deposition of Espinhaço Supergroup basal units such as the formation Bandeirinha and São João da Chapada in Southern Espinhaço, São Simão in Northern Espinhaço, and Novo Horizonte in Chapada Diamantina (Fig. 9; Brito-Neves et al., 1995; Dussin and Dussin 1995; Chemale-Júnior et al., 2010, 2011);
- deposition of Araí Group basal units, which crop out in the northeastern Brasília belt (Brito Neves et al., 1995);
- extrusion of a considerable volume of bimodal volcanic lava in the bottom part of Espinhaço Supergroup (Brito Neves et al., 1995; Danderfer et al., 2009; Chemale-Júnior et al., 2011);
- Borrachudos Suite intrusion, which crops out in the southeastern Araçuaí belt. The suite consists of anorogenic granites dated circa 1.75 Ga (Grossi Sad et al., 1990; Dussin et al., 1994; Chemale-Júnior et al., 1998; Silva et al., 2002);
- Lagoa Real Complex protolith and other coeval plutons (e.g. São Timóteo granite) that intruded the basement along the Paramirim Aulacogen axis (Turpin et al., 1988; Cordani et al., 1992; Pimentel et al., 1994; Cruz, 2004; Cruz et al., 2007);

Fig. 4. The Transamazonian orogeny (2.3-2.05 Ga) assembled the Archean blocks (Gavião, Jequié, Serrinha and Itabuna-Salvador-Curaçá) and established the basement for the Espinhaço and São Francisco supergroups in São Francisco craton and Chapada

Fig. 5. a) The São Francisco craton's evolution: a) Paleoproterozoic Transamazonian orogeny resulted from the collision between Gavião and Gabon blocks circa 2.08 Ga; b) Statherian rift (1.8-1.6 Ga) triggered an ensialic system that is recorded in Espinhaço

Supergroup and correlative units; c) the Tonian rift and Macaúbas passive margins (850 Ma); d) Brazilian collision assembled the Gondwana continent and the orogenic belts that limit the São Francisco craton (520 Ma); e) Gondwana break-up in the Lower Cretaceous and the onset of Recôncavo-Tucano-Jatobá, Abaeté and other interior rifting (Alkmim, 2004).

Ma	BRASILIA BELT	SÃO FRANCISCO CRATON				WEST CONGOLIAN BELT	CONGO CRATON	EVENTS	SUPER-CONTINENTS
		Quadrilátero Ferrífero	S. Francisco basin	Araçuaí Belt Southern Espinhaço Range	Paramirim aulacogen Northern Espinhaço Range				
542	Rio Verde Fm	Bambu Group		Salitre Fm	Salitre Fm	Upper West-Congo Group	Brasiliano/PanAfrican orogeny Marinoan	Gondwanaland	
630									
850	Cubatão Fm Canastra Group	Vazante Group Jequitai Fm	Macaúbas Group	Bebedouro Fm	Bebedouro Fm	Lower West-Congo Gr Mayumbian Group Zadrianian Group	E7 Sturtian Adamastor ocean Continental rifting	Rodinia	
1000							E6 Sangha aulacogen		
1200	Paranoá Group	Conselheiro Mata Group	Conselheiro Mata Gr Sopa, Galho Miguel Fms	S. Marcos Group	UE Caboclo and M. Chapéu Fms	Chela Group Kibaran Group	E5 Rift-sag basin		
1400					MEI Tombador Fm	Karagwe-Ankolian & Kunene Complex	E3 Extensional intraplate		
1600					MEI Bomba Fm and correlatives		E2 Extensional		
1800	Araçuaí Group		S.J. Chapada Fm. Bandeirinha Fm	O. Brejinhos Group	LEI R. Remédios Group		E1 Continental rifting		
2050									
2300	Itacolomi Group					Francevillian	TransAmazonian / Eburnean orogeny	Columbia	
2500	Minas Supergroup					Ogooué Group	Makganyene Minas orogeny		

Fig. 6. Seven extensional and/or anarogenic tectonic events occurred before the establishment of the orogenic belts that border the São Francisco-Congo craton (modified from Pedrosa-Soares and Alkmim, 2011 and Guadagnin et al., 2015).

Calymmian synclises (1.57-1.5 Ga): The second older magmatic and extensional tectonism event is recorded at the medium portion of Espinhaço Supergroup in the Paramirim Aulacogen. This event is represented in the Southern Espinhaço by alluvial and aeolian sandstones and acid to intermediate volcanic rocks from Bomba Formation (U-Pb age of 1582 ± 8 Ma and 1569 ± 14 Ma; Danderfer et al., 2009). In Chapada Diamantina, alluvial and aeolian sandstones from Mangabeira Formation intruded by tholeiitic mafic dikes dated at 1514 ± 22 Ma (Babinski et al., 1999) and 1501 ± 9.1 Ma (Silveira et al., 2013). In the Araçuaí orogen, rare 1.51-1.57 Ga detrital zircons occur at the upper portion of the Espinhaço Supergroup (Babinski et al., 2011; Chemale-Júnior et al., 2011; Gonçalves-Dias et al., 2011). This event is yet to be documented in Western Congo and Congo craton surrounding areas (Tack et al., 2001);

NeoEctasian intraplate extension (1.416-1.375 Ga): This regimen is associated with voluminous type S and A granitoid and mafic to ultramafic complexes found in the: Karagwe-Ankolian belt at eastern Congo (Tack et al., 2010; Fernandez-Alonso et al., 2012), Kunene complex and related granites in western Congo (Ernst et al., 2013). In Chapada Diamantina, a recent SHRIMP dating from detrital zircons and volcanic crystal-tuff from the Upper Tombador Formation indicates the maximum age of 1394 ± 14 Ma (Gruber et al., 2011) and 1416 ± 28 Ma (Guadagnin et al., 2015) for this unit. The Tombador Formation overlies the unconformity with the Açuruá Formation, which is also demonstrated through a depocenter shift from the east (associated with Açuruá Formation) to the west (related to Tombador Formation) as shown by palaeocurrent readings (Pedreira, 1994). The volcanic activity, unconformity and paleocurrent shift suggest intraplate reorganisation

before and/or during the deposition of the Lower Tombador Formation. More likely, such reorganisation was triggered by extensional events in the Congo craton (Guadagnin et al., 2015), creating a new cycle of sag basin formation in the interior of the São Francisco craton. The sin-depositional volcanism at 1.42 Ga has not been identified in other units of the Espinhaço Supergroup;

NeoStenian rifting (1.18 - ? Ga): As recently proposed by Chemale Jr et al. (2010, 2011), the thick package of alluvial, aeolian and marine strata from Medium to Upper Espinhaço Supergroup observed in the Araçuaí belt, such as Sopa-Brumadinho Formation and overlying units, stand for a rift-sag sequence (Dussin and Dussin, 1995; Uhlein et al., 1998; Martins-Neto, 2000), whose deposition started around 1.18 Ga. During this event, Statherian rift systems were reactivated and expanded to host the abovementioned units. However, it is not certain when the event finished. In the western Congo and adjacent areas, no evidence of the event has been found (Pedrosa-Soares and Alkmim, 2011);

Stenian-Tonian rifting (ca. 1 Ga): The anarogenic magmatism is recorded in western Congo and is represented by type A granites called Noquis Granite, aged at 999 ± 7 Ma (Tack et al., 2001). This anarogenic suite registers the event E5, which was probably created by an extensional episode related to the Sangha Aulacogen opening. Mafic dikes of similar ages found in western Bahia State (Renne et al., 1990), at the eastern São Francisco craton, are potentially correlated with the event E5. Circa 1.0 Ga, the Rodinia supercontinent was assembled by Greenville orogeny, but no evidence of such orogeny has been found in Chapada Diamantina;

Tonian tafrogenese (ca 950 Ma): During this tafrogenese, Statherian rifts were reactivated, and some evolved to passive margins during Rodinia break up. The São Francisco-Congo plate was individualised;

Tonian rifting (930-850 Ma): Its principal record is the thick bimodal volcanic deposit from Zadinian and Mayumbian groups and related intrusions that occur in western Congo. The Zadinian Group records rift deposits of siliciclastic strata and peralkaline rhyolite covered by a thick succession of mafic volcanic rocks. The Mayumbian Group is more than 4 km thick and is formed by felsic volcanic rocks intruded by abundant cogenetic bodies of monzo-sienogranite and some alkali-felspathic granites subordinately interbedded with sedimentary rocks. The Mayumbian volcanics were dated by SHRIMP U–Pb from zircons at 920 ± 8 Ma in the lower portion and at 912 ± 7 Ma in the upper part (Tack et al., 2001). The Zadinian and younger Mayumbian magmatism are examples of bimodal suites formed during the onset of a continental rift (Tack et al., 2001). Besides, anarogenic granites and gabbros aged between ca. 904 Ma and ca. 867 Ma (Thieblemont et al., 2011) mark the event E6 in the Gabon sector of the western Congo belt;

Mafic dikes and anarogenic granites are the most important record of this event in the Araçuaí belt and São Francisco craton. The Pedro Lessa mafic dike swarm (906 ± 7 Ma) registers the event E6 in Northern Espinhaço, and basic dikes (ca. 850 Ma) mark the event in Southern Espinhaço (Danderfer et al., 2009). Type A granites from the Salto da Divisa suite (875 ± 9 Ma; Silva et al., 2008) represent this event along the northeastern Araçuaí belt and São Francisco craton. Although the Macaúbas basin subsidence mechanism is not well constrained, Pedrosa-Soares and Alkmim (2011) consider that deposition without diamictites (pre-glacial) from the lower portion of Macaúbas Group, which is composed of breccias, conglomerates and sandstones, may have occurred a rift phase related to E6 event (Pedrosa-Soares et al., 2008, 2011a; Martins et al., 2008; Babinski et al., 2011);

Cryogenian event (750-670 Ma): The primary record consists of voluminous alkaline intrusions that make up the alkaline province southwest of Bahia State. These anarogenic intrusions, aged between ca. 735 Ma and ca. 675 Ma, include peralkaline to sub-alkaline rocks that occur in the eastern domain of the São Francisco craton,

close to the border with the Araçuaí belt (Teixeira et al., 1997). In Gabon, northeastern from the Congo western belt, La Louila Formation exhibits rhyolites and rhyolitic tuffs with a maximum age of 713 ± 49 Ma (Thieblemont et al., 2011), representing the Cryogenian magmatism. The glaciogenic diamictites from the Macaúbas Group and their correlatives in the western Congo belt and cratonic domains (such as Jequitaí and Bebedouro formations) are more likely representative sedimentary records of this event. The attempts to define the age of mafic volcanic rocks interbedded with glacial diamictites from the Macaúbas Group have not been successful (Babinski et al., 2005, 2011). Available data indicate these units were formed between 900 Ma and 740 Ma (Babinski et al., 2011; Pedrosa-Soares et al., 2011a). The minimal age of 740 ± 22 Ma (Babinski et al., 2007) was determined at the lower portion of the Sete Lagoas Formation. This cap-carbonate overlies the glaciogenic deposits of the Jequitaí Formation in the interior of the São Francisco craton;

Brazilian orogeny: According to Delgado et al., 2003, the Brazilian orogeny is divided into Brazilian I (ca. 900-700 Ma) with a collisional peak at 790 Ma; Brazilian II (ca. 650-600 Ma) with a collisional peak at 632 Ma; and Brazilian III (ca. 590-520 Ma) that culminated at 520 Ma. Collisions around the borders of the São Francisco craton assembled the Western Gondwana continent at the end of the Neoproterozoic. Passive margins were transformed into orogenic belts that define the craton current limits. In the continent's interior, a foreland basin was formed, triggering the deposition of the Bambuí/Salitre formations. At the same time, some rifts were partially inverted and lately, the thrusting partially affected strata from Bambuí/Salitre formations;

Gondwana break-up and the South Atlantic opening: The break-up of Gondwana in the Cretaceous give birth to Abaeté and Recôncavo-Tucano-Jatobá rifts as well as the Brazilian and Western Africa passive margins.

5. Chapada Diamantina

The Chapada Diamantina area is subdivided into the Western and Eastern Domains (Jardim de Sá et al., 1976). This course is restricted to the Eastern Domain, in which the sedimentary cover is folded in a set of anticlines and synclines with re-folded hinge lines oriented to NNW-SSE, whose wavelength increase from west to east (Figs. 7, 8).

Fig. 7. Northward view of the Pai Inácio anticline (Magalhães et al., 2007). The positive topography results from Lower Tombador Formation cemented sandstones, which are much more resistant to the erosion than fine-grained rocks from Açuruá Formation cropping out along the anticline hinge.

The predominant structural pattern in this region corresponds to a system of folds and thrust faults oriented to NNW-SSE and N-S (Danderfer (1990). This author recognised four structural domains in Chapada Diamantina with different deformation grades and structural styles: Morro do Chapéu (which encompasses this course study area), Irecê, Gentio do Ouro and Piatã. The Morro do Chapéu domain exhibits relatively low to minor deformation, which allows the analysis of primary sedimentary structures. Folds are smooth and opened, without noticeable vergency, with the axis oriented approximately N-S. It also presents thrust faults with eastward vergency (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Chapada Diamantina geologic map. The Barra do Mendes-João Correia (BJ) lineament separates the eastern and western domains (Cruz and Alkmim, 2007). Abreviatura: ES – Western Espinhaço.

In lithostratigraphic terms, this course follows the nomenclature as proposed in Bahia State Geologic Map (Barbosa and Dominguez, 1994). The sedimentary cover in Chapada Diamantina (Espinhaço and São Francisco Basins) overlies the Transamazonian basement and composes the Espinhaço and São Francisco Supergroups (Inda and Barbosa, 1978). The Supergroup Espinhaço in Chapada Diamantina (Figs. 9 and 10) consists of Rio dos Remédios, Paraguaçu and Chapada Diamantina Groups.

Fig. 9. Stratigraphic chart of the Espinhaço Supergroup (Magalhães et al., 2016, modified from Guadagnin et al. 2015). This course focuses on the Mangabeira and Tombador formations. Note the significant hiatuses related to unconformities that limit lithostratigraphic units (e.g. SU1 and SU8). Actually, the unconformities limit distinct basin fills. Therefore, they are ranked as 1st order unconformities that limit 1st order depositional sequence (Catuneanu 2006, 2022).

Rio dos Remédios Group: it is composed of acid volcanic (rhyolites, dacites, trachytes, tuffs and volcanic breccias) and metasedimentary rocks (quartzites, conglomerates and schists). Pedreira (1994) interpreted these deposits as representative of the alluvial fan depositional system; Danderfer (1990) shows evidence that supports fluvial, aeolian, deltaic and marine depositional systems.

Paraguaçu Group: it is formed by Mangabeira and Açuruá formations. The lower portion of the Mangabeira Formation contains pink-coloured, fine- to medium-grained fluvial sandstone and some conglomeratic levels. The upper part of the Mangabeira Formation consists of aeolian cross-bedded sandstones interbedded with pelitic levels (Souza, 2012). The Açuruá Formation is formed by marine and deltaic mudstone, siltstone, and sandstone (Magalhães et al., 2015).

Fig. 10. Schematic stratigraphic chart of the Espinhaço Supergroup in Chapada Diamantina (Bállico et al., 2017). Hiatuses between lithostratigraphic units are associated with 1st order unconformities (vide Fig. 9).

Chapada Diamantina Group: It comprises Tombador, Caboclo, and Morro do Chapéu formations. The Tombador Formation is the most studied unit in this course. The Lower part consists of sandstone, siltstone and mudstone deposited in fluvial, estuarine and shallow marine environments. The Upper portion is characterised by a continental alluvial fan (Lavras conglomerate), fluvial and aeolian sandstone, and less expressive mudstone/siltstone strata (Silva Born, 2011; Bállico, 2012; Scherer and Magalhães, 2013; Magalhães et al., 2014b, 2016).

Caboclo Formation: It is represented by siliciclastic mudstone to sandstone and carbonate marine strata (Ferronato et al., 2021). Morro do Chapéu Formation is formed by deposits representative of alluvial fan, fluvial and shallow marine depositional systems (Souza et al., 2019).

São Francisco Supergroup: This unit is only represented by Una Group in Chapada Diamantina, and is subdivided into Bebedouro and Salitre formations. Bebedouro Formation is composed of strata deposited in glacial and alluvial fan environments. Salitre Formation consists of fully marine carbonate strata deposited in a shallow ramp setting.

Fig. 11. Photography and GPR line (400 MHz) of outcrop 1 (vide Figs. 1 and 2), Mangabeira Formation close to Seabra city. Sandy strata are cyclically interbedded with pelitic intervals with remarkable continuity in the subsurface (Magalhães et al., 2017).

6. Stratigraphic analysis based on sequence stratigraphy

Sequence stratigraphy is a stratigraphic analysis method based on recognising stratal stacking patterns using the available data from the study area. Stratal stacking patterns (progradational, aggradational, degradational and retrogradational) are independent of scale and control mechanisms. This approach is based on sedimentary processes and enables the understanding of the distribution pattern of sediments during the evolution of sedimentary basins, as well as the prediction of the occurrence of depositional facies associations beyond the control points. For this reason, sequence stratigraphy is applied to clastic, carbonate and evaporite depositional systems in sedimentary basins formed in the most diverse tectonic settings (Catuneanu, 2006, 2019, 2022; Magalhães et al., 2020, 2021).

The scale of a stratigraphic analysis may be regional (i.e. low resolution and generally based on seismic data) or local (i.e. high resolution, below seismic resolution and generally based on outcrops, cores or well logs). In high resolution, stacking patterns are recognised through the vertical succession of architectural elements. There are four criteria to identify a high-resolution sequence: i) typical internal T-R pattern; ii) vertical recurrence of the signature of stacking patterns at each considered hierarchy; iii) trends (non-random distribution) of the vertical arrangement of stacking patterns that determine high-frequency sequences as the basis for defining and building the systems tracts of immediately higher-order sequences; iv) mappability of the stacking patterns and their respective bounding stratigraphic surfaces at each considered hierarchy (Magalhães et al., 2020; Fragoso et al., 2021).

6.1. Stratigraphic analysis of aeolian successions (Mangabeira Fm)

An aeolian succession crops out with remarkable cyclicity of sandstone and siltstone. The architectural elements are easily recognised on the outcrop based on lithology, sedimentary structures and GPR facies (dunes, sand sheets and flooding deposits; Fig. 11), which are organised in several depositional cycles (Fig. 12; Souza, 2012; Bállico et al., 2017).

Fig. 12. Sedimentologic log of outcrop 1 (vide Figs. 1 and 2), Mangabeira Formation close to Seabra city. Note the depositional upward wetting and drying cycles (wetting in black and drying in white; Souza, 2012).

The challenge in this outcrop consists of recognising the architectural elements and their stacking pattern, interpreting stratigraphic surfaces and unravelling the high-frequency cyclicity. Once the sedimentological logs elaborated by the participants are integrated, they elect which high-resolution surface is a candidate to belong to the immediately higher rank and identify the related systems tract. This analysis triggers discussions regarding analogue aeolian reservoir zonation and the strategies one should use to optimise production and oil recovery factor.

6.2. Stratigraphic analysis of fluvial, estuarine and shallow marine successions (Tombador Sequence)

The subaerial unconformity SU1 marks the boundary between two distinct intracratonic sag basin fills: the Mangabeira/Açuruá and the Tombador basins (Magalhães et al., 2016). The basin fill during a specific tectonic setting consists of a 1st order depositional sequence. Its subdivision represents 2nd order (Catuneanu 2006, 2022). The Paraguaçu Group represents the 1st order Middle Espinhaço I sequence (ME-I). The Tombador Formation stands for the 1st order Middle Espinhaço II sequence (ME-II), which is bounded at the bottom and the top by SU1 and SU8, respectively. The hiatuses associated with these unconformities are approximately 100 Ma and 300 Ma, respectively (Figs. 9 and 15; Magalhães et al., 2016).

SU1 is easily mapped on the digital terrain model (Fig. 13), Serra do Mucugezinho cliff (the first that forms the 3 Irmãos sightseeing, Fig. 14), Pai Inácio hill and Ponte outcrop (Figs. 1 and 2).

Fig. 13. Digital terrain model (based on SRTM data) and SU1 (in red) between the Tombador and Açuruá formations. These units are recognised because they show distinct photofacies calibrated with sedimentological logs of outcrops. Southward view from outcrop 4 as shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 14. SU1 (red arrow) on Mucugezinho hill marks the contact between the Açuruá and Tombador formations. Southward view to Capão Valley from outcrop 4 (Figs. 1 and 2). Mucugezinho hill is the first that makes up 3 Irmãos sightseeing.

ME-II sequence is composed of two 2nd order sequences separated by subaerial unconformity SU6: the Lower and the Upper (Fig. 15). SU6 separates two distinct depositional contexts. The Lower 2nd order sequence records fluvial, estuarine and shallow marine sedimentation. In lithostratigraphic terms, this unit is represented by Lower Tombador Formation. In contrast, the Upper 2nd order sequence only registers continental strata representative of alluvial fan (Fig. 16), fluvial and aeolian depositional systems. In lithostratigraphic terms, this unit is represented by Upper Tombador Formation.

The overall regression represented by the entirely continental deposits from the 2nd order Superior sequence resulted from a tectonic tilt that enhanced the original limits of the Tombador Basin (Bállico, 2012, Guadagnin et al., 2015a). The tectonic reorganisation modified the depositional context and sediment palaeoflows. Therefore, SU6 is a stratigraphic surface that subdivides the Tombador Basin fill, and hence it separates 2nd order depositional sequences (Fig. 15; Magalhães et al., 2016).

The Lower 2nd order sequence crops out and sustains the positive topography around the hinge area of the Pai Inácio anticline (Figs. 7, 13 and 14). In contrast, the Upper 2nd order sequence occurs on both limbs of the anticline with an unconformable contact and is overlaid by 1st order Upper Espinhaço (UE) sequence (Figs. 15 and 17).

Datum: base da seção pelítica Fm. Caboclo

Fig. 15. Depositional strike stratigraphic cross-section of the Chapada Diamantina. ME-II 1st order sequence (basin fill of Tombador sag basin) is bounded at the base and top by SU1 and SU8, respectively. SU6 divides ME-II into the Lower (in green) and Upper (in orange) 2nd order sequences. SU6, recognised at the base of continental strata truncating estuarine or shallow-marine deposits, marks a tectonic tilt that enhanced the original limits of the Tombador Basin and triggered an overall regression (Bálico, 2012; Magalhães et al., 2016). Noteworthy, the diamond prone conglomerate (Lavras conglomerate) only occurs in the Superior 2nd order sequence (Fig. 16). Radiometric dating follows Guadagnin et al., 2015 (Fig. 9).

Fig. 17. SU8 unconformity at the easter limb of the Pai Inácio anticline (red arrow) at Lençóis city. Note people standing on a conglomerate bed (Upper 2nd order sequence) and vegetated soil from weathering of the Upper Espinhaço (UE) 1st order sequence (Caboclo Fm in this location).

Fig. 16. Alluvial fan deposits (informally called Lavras conglomerate and prone in diamonds in Chapada Diamantina) only occur in the Upper 2nd order sequence. This unit is represented by the Upper Tombador Formation (Magalhães et al., 2016).

The Pai Inácio hill exhibits 125 m thick succession of the Lower 2nd order sequence. This unit unconformable overlies ME-I sequence, in this place represented by deltaic strata from Açuruá Formation (Fig. 18).

The Lower 2nd order sequence is characterized by 3rd order transgressive-regressive (T-R) cycles. Indeed, these cycles represent 3rd order depositional sequences lowstand, transgressive and highstand systems tracts, which are characterised by fluvial, estuarine and shallow-marine deposits, respectively. In turn, 3rd order systems tracts are formed by genetic 4th order sequences that establishes the reservoir zonation at this outcrop scale. Such a cyclicity is detailed worked in this course (Fig. 19).

Fig. 18. The Pai Inácio hill exhibits a great portion of the Lower 2nd order sequence overlying SU1 (red line). Note several horizontal grooves within this unit. GR was logged at each 20 cm, the same used in well logs (Magalhães et al., 2016).

SU1 is well exposed and easily accessed at the Ponte outcrop (Fig. 20). It is noteworthy that, both in Pai Inácio hill and Ponte outcrops, sequence ME-II transgressive estuarine deposits rest over SU1. Such a contact indicates tide-ravinement surface (TRS) superimposed SU1. Moreover, it also indicates the 3rd order lowstand systems tract was not preserved in these locations (Figs. 9, 19, 20 and 21).

Fig. 20. SU1 as seen on the Ponte outcrop. Note the change of palaeoflux direction through the unconformity: eastward (below, longitudinal accretion bar, Açuruá Fm) and westward (above, cross-bedded tidal bar, Tombador Fm).

Fig. 19. The Lower 2nd order sequence is subdivided into 3rd order depositional sequences, which in turn is formed by 4th order genetic sequences. The latter establishes the reservoir zonation in this outcrop (Magalhães et al., 2016; Fragoso et al., 2020).

Fig. 21. Superimposed SU1 and TRS surfaces between estuarine and deltaic deposits (Tombador and Açuruá formations, respectively), as seen on 400 MHz GPR line on the Ponte outcrop. In this location, the lowstand systems tract is missing. High-resolution sequence stratigraphic surfaces are indicated in red (subaerial unconformity, SU), blue (tide ravinement surface - TRS) and green (maximum flooding surface; Magalhães et al., 2017).

The palaeogeographic reconstruction at the end of the oldest 4th order transgressive systems tract illustrates the shift of depositional setting and depocenters' location through SU1 (Fig. 22).

Fig. 22. Palaeogeographic reconstructions based on 4th order systems tracts are representative of the depositional settings changes through SU1: a regressive (deltaic) system is recorded at the upper portion of the ME-I whereas transgressive (shallow marine, estuarine, coastal and continental) systems are documented at the lower portion of the ME-II first order sequences (Magalhães et al., 2015, 2016).

The stacking pattern demonstrated by the vertical recurrence of architectural elements is recognised from the sedimentological logs built by participants, with the support of GPR lines and outcrop orthophotos. 4th order sequences are then identified through the internal T-R pattern, its vertical recurrence, the analysis of their trends to identify sequences of immediate superior hierarchy, and the mappability of intervals with the same stacking pattern and bounding surfaces (Magalhães et al., 2020; Fragoso et al., 2021). 4th order sequences compose 3rd order systems tracts (Fig. 19). Participants are encouraged to identify 3rd order candidate sequence stratigraphic surfaces during the presentation of sedimentological logs in front of outcrops and the integration of all sedimentological logs in the hotel. During these debates, participants also discuss the identification of 5th order sequences.

The stratigraphic refinement achieved through the identification and correlation of 4th order sequences enables rich discussions regarding reservoir zonation and characterisation. The course's exercises reinforce the high-resolution sequence stratigraphic method and its application in the petroleum industry. At the end of each exercise, a favourable moment is established to discuss strategies focused on selecting the best reservoir to start production in new oil fields and optimising production and increasing of oil recovery factor in mature fields. The exercise on reservoir zonation and identification of an oil zone with original pressure from a mature onshore Brazilian field is worth mentioning. Revising the reservoir zonation and identifying oil zones not yet drained oriented workover operations and in-fill drilling to produce the target oil. These actions triggered the increase in production and oil recovery factor. Such a real example of field rejuvenation proves the advantage of using high-resolution sequence stratigraphy. It motivates participants to apply it in their routines back in their offices.

7. Final remarks

This is a methodological and practical field course that is founded on the recognition of stacking patterns, identification of sequence stratigraphic surfaces and systems tracts, and the hierarchical ordering of stratigraphic sequences from the basin fill during a tectonic phase (1st order unit) to high-frequency reservoir zonation and characterisation (4th order units in the study area).

Starting from the "learn by doing" assumption, this course is an opportunity for participants to refine their knowledge and improve their skills in stratigraphic analyses based on up-to-date sequence stratigraphy. Using MVAs to integrate several data with the sedimentological logs enable participants to propose and test interpretations using 3D virtual models, mimicking the current practice in vogue in the industry and academy.

High-resolution sequence stratigraphy is the current paradigm of reservoir geology. Experiencing real and concrete situations throughout the course facilitates its comprehension and encourages its application in the participants' work routines. Therefore, the *Field Course Sequence Stratigraphy (Chapada Diamantina, Bahia) – from the basin fill to reservoir zonation* consists of an outstanding training opportunity, experience and learning exchange, perhaps unique in the world.

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ANNEXE: Outcrop's location

Outcrop 1: Seabra outcrop. Approximately 300 m in length with cyclical aeolian deposits.

Activity: Description and stratigraphic analysis.

Location: BR-242 road, 2 km westward from Seabra city (12°25'50''S / 41°47'05''W)

Unit: Mangabeira Fm.

Outcrop 2: Diamictite. Approximately 50 m in length with periglacial deposits.

Activity: Visit to observe some glacial deposits, especially the dropstone.

Location: BR-242 road, 3,2 km westward of the road junction towards Palmeiras city (12°27'33''S / 41°37'03''W)

Unit: Bebedouro Fm.

Outcrop 3: Pai Inácio hill (1,120 m altitude) and 250 m high, of which 125 m exposes strata from Tombador Fm. The uppermost 50 m are easily accessible by a track up to the summit.

Activity: 1- Orthophoto based interpretation of depositional systems, stacking pattern, stratigraphic surfaces and 3rd order depositional sequences. Interpretation of the uppermost 3rd order sequence. 2- Description and stratigraphic analysis in the 3rd and 4th orders throughout the track. Comparison with pre-description interpretation.

Location: BR-242 road (12°28'10''S / 41°27'21''W)

Unit: Fm. Tombador.

Outcrop 4: South view of Pai Inácio anticline (Bahia State geodesic centre). Located at the anticlinal hinge, the southward view enables the anticline geometry and SU1 identification, the unconformity that separates two 1st order sequences represented by Açuruá (below) and Tombador (above) formations.

Activity: Visit for regional contextualisation.

Location: BR-242 road (12°27'55''S / 41°27'29''W).

Unit: Fm. Tombador.

Outcrop 5: Ponte outcrop. SU1 unconformity, close to the western road bridge abutment.

Activity: Visit for regional contextualisation. SU1 is recognised at the contact between deltaic architectural elements (longitudinal accretion bars prograding eastward, distributary channel, Açuruá Fm) and estuarine tidal bars (westward cross-bedded strata, Tombador Fm). SU1 reinforces the occurrence of the most basal succession of the ME-II sequence (the basal portion of the Lower Tombador Fm).

Location: BR-242 road bridge over Mucugezinho river (12°28'12''S / 41°26'36''W).

Unit: Fm. Tombador.

Outcrop 5 - continuation: Estuarine, shallow-marine and fluvial successions, a few metres eastward from the bridge.

Activity: Description and identification of architectural elements, recognising stacking patterns, adjusting pre-field work interpretation on orthophotos, identification of 4th order sequence stratigraphic surfaces and. Identification of SU2 at the base or fluvial strata.

Location: BR-242 road bridge over Mucugezinho river (12°28'12''S / 41°26'36''W).

Unit: Tombador Fm.

Outcrop 6: Pelé outcrop. Estuarine succession approximately 200 m in length, in front of Pelé stand.

Activity: Visit to recognise estuarine architectural elements and stratigraphic positioning, comparing with interpreted sequences on Pai Inácio hill's orthophoto.

Location: BR-242 road (12°27'58''S / 41°26'05''W).

Unit: Tombador Fm.

Outcrop 6 - continuation: Fluvial deposits, some metres eastward from Pele stand.

Activity: Visit to recognise fluvial strata and stratigraphic positioning, comparing with interpreted sequences on Pai Inácio hill's orthophoto.

Location: BR-242 road (12°27'53''S / 41°25'46''W).

Unit: Tombador Fm.

Outcrop 7: Mengão outcrop. Estuarine succession approximately 200 m in length.

Activity: Visit to recognise estuarine architectural elements and stratigraphic positioning, comparing with interpreted sequences on Pai Inácio hill's orthophoto.

Location: BR-242 road (12°27'49''S / 41°25'36''W).

Unit: Tombador Fm.

Outcrop 7 - continuation: Fluvial deposits, some metres westward from Hotel outdoor outcrop.

Activity: Visit to recognise fluvial strata and stratigraphic positioning, comparing with interpreted sequences on Pai Inácio hill's orthophoto.

Location: BR-242 road (12°27'46''S / 41°25'28''W).

Unit: Tombador Fm.

Outcrop 8: Hotel outdoor outcrop. Estuarine succession approximately 20 m in length.

Activity: Visit to recognise estuarine architectural elements and stratigraphic positioning, comparing with interpreted sequences on Pai Inácio hill's orthophoto and the uppermost sequence.

Location: BR-242 road (12°27'45''S / 41°25'27''W).

Unit: Tombador Fm.

Outcrop 9: Toca da Rita access. Tide-influenced fluvial deposits some metres eastward from the Hotel outdoor outcrop.

Activity: Visit to recognise fluvial strata and stratigraphic positioning, comparing with interpreted sequences on Pai Inácio hill's orthophoto and the uppermost sequence.

Location: BR-242 road (12°27'44''S / 41°25'14''W).

Unit: Tombador Fm.

Outcrop 10: Mucugezinho river. Fluvial succession along Mucugezinho river.

Activity: Walking to Loro stand to recognise fluvial and aeolian architectural elements strata and stratigraphic positioning, comparing with interpreted sequences on Pai Inácio hill's orthophoto and the uppermost sequence.

Location: Mucugezinho river bed, between Toca da Rita and Loro stand (12°27'38''S / 41°25'10''W).

Unit: Tombador Fm.

Outcrop 10 - continuation: Fluvial, aeolian and tide-influenced fluvial deposits some metres eastward from Loro stand by BR-242 road.

Activity: Visit to recognise architectural elements and stratigraphic positioning, comparing with interpreted sequences on Pai Inácio hill's orthophoto and the uppermost sequence.

Location: BR-242 road (12°27'49''S / 41°25'06''W).

Unit: Tombador Fm.

Outcrop 11: Lavras conglomerate. Conglomerate deposits some metres eastward from Loro stand by BR-242 road.

Activity: View from BR-242 road to recognise conglomerate deposit and stratigraphic positioning, comparing with interpreted sequences on Pai Inácio hill's orthophoto. This unit belongs to the Upper 2nd order sequence (the Upper Tombador Fm).

Location: BR-242 road (12°28'00''S / 41°24'56''W).

Unit: Tombador Fm.

Outcrop 12: Serrano. Conglomerate (Lavras) deposits on the Lençóis river bed. Currently, this place is part of Muritiba Park.

Activity: Visit to recognise conglomerate deposits representative of alluvial fans and evidence of diamond-digging. This unit belongs to the Upper 2nd order sequence (the Upper Tombador Fm).

Location: Lençóis river bed (12°33'50''S / 41°23'53''W).

Unit: Tombador Fm, Lavras conglomerate.

Outcrop 13: Rodi dune. Aeolian deposits cropping out on the southwestern margin of the Lençóis river. This aeolian dune was first recognised by geologist Rodi Ávila Medeiros and named after him.

Activity: Visit to recognise aeolian deposits associated with alluvial fan conglomerate and fluvial strata. This unit belongs to the Upper 2nd order sequence (the Upper Tombador Fm). This is the last outcrop visited in this course.

Location: Lençóis river (12°33'33''S / 41°24'17''W).

Unit: Tombador Fm.